

IPBES VA Chapter 5. Differences between future archetypes (text similarity analysis)

Code: IPBES_VA_5.4

Versioning: 02 (14.03.2022)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4380980

Project leader(s)

Zuzana Harmáčková (harmackova.z@czechglobe.cz)

Aidin Niamir (niamir@gmail.com)

Researcher(s)

Yuki Yoshida (y.yoshida.tokyo@gmail.com)

Ellen Guimaraes (ellen.guimaraes@senckenberg.de)

Data curator(s)

Ellen Guimaraes (ellen.guimaraes@senckenberg.de)

Description: This analysis corresponds to the IPBES Values Assessment Chapter 5. The methodology explained in this report highlights the types of conceptualizations of the value of nature and its benefits to people that have not been explicitly addressed or have not been explicitly incorporated into decision-making; and the types of valuation approaches, as well as their articulation, integration and bridging, that are underdeveloped or have not been explicitly incorporated into decision-making. A review using text analysis of peer-reviewed scenarios, visions and pathways (257 documents) is followed in order to assess the similarity between qualitative descriptions of drivers and impacts across groups of archetypes (3).

Protocol:

The data set is composed of 234 scenarios, 7 archetypes, and 5 drivers/impacts.

The following abbreviations were used for archetypes and drivers/impacts:

- Archetypes:
 - gsd = Global Sustainability Development
 - rs = Regional Sustainability
 - bau = Business as Usual

- eo = Economic Optimism
- rc = Regional Competition
- ineq = Inequality
- br = Breakdown
- Drivers/Impacts:
 - dir = direct drivers
 - ind = indirect drivers
 - nat = Nature impacts
 - ncp = nature contribution to people impacts
 - gqol = global quality of life impact

To test different assumptions about the relations between drivers, impacts/archetypes 3 aggregation options were defined for the application of text similarity.

Aggregation options:

- Aggregation option A:
 - Direct + Indirect drivers together
- Aggregation option B:
 - Direct + Indirect drivers together
 - Impacts on Nature, NCPs, and GQoL together
- Aggregation option C:
 - Direct + Indirect drivers together
 - Impacts on nature, ncp, and gqol together
 - Archetypes aggregated as follows:
 - bau + eo
 - gsd + rs
 - rc + ineq + br

1. Data Processing:

For the text-similarity computation of the dataset, the following steps and methodologies were applied:

- Programming language:
 - Python 3
- Preprocessing
 - Tokenization
 - Cleaning
 - Stop words removal
 - Punctuation, Symbols, and numbers removal
 - Words with less than 2 characters

- Stemming
- Term frequency - Inverse document frequency (TFIDF)
- Cosine similarity

For each aggregation option, a CSV table containing the coefficient of similarity was created and a heat map figure in png format was plotted.

The programming language used was Python 3.

The code is stored in a GitHub repository.

File Descriptions

Name	File Type	Size	Description
vach5_textsim_optionA_table.csv	CSV	15 KB	Table with similarity coefficients of Aggregation Option A
vach5_textsim_optionA.html	HTML	955 KB	Jupyter notebook in html format
vach5_textsim_optionA_matrix1.png	PNG	315 KB	Heat map of the results of the Aggregation A
vach5_textsim_optionA.py	PY	6 KB	Python scripts using the rules of Aggregation A
vach5_textsim_optionB_table.csv	CSV	4 KB	Table with similarity coefficients of Aggregation Option B
vach5_textsim_optionB.html	HTML	524 KB	Jupyter notebook in html format
vach5_textsim_optionB_matrix1.png	PNG	110 KB	Heat map of the results of the Aggregation B
vach5_textsim_optionB.py	PY	5 KB	Python scripts using the rules of Aggregation B
vach5_textsim_optionC_table.csv	CSV	810	Table with similarity coefficients

		bytes	of Aggregation Option C
vach5_textsim_optionC.html	HTML	370 KB	Jupyter notebook in html format
vach5_textsim_optionC_matrix1.png	PNG	40 KB	Heat map of the results of the Aggregation C
vach5_textsim_optionC.py	PY	5 KB	Python scripts using the rules of Aggregation C